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COMPARATIVE YIELD AND ANALYSIS OF ALCOHOL FROM SELECTED AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS

¹Aigbovo, Nicholas Naruna,²Oviawe, Amowie.Philip,¹Peretiemo-Clark, Beatrice Oghenetega

¹Department of chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State

²Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences, Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria

Corresponding author's email: Nigeria. Phone number: nicholas.aigbovo@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Alcohol was produced from cassava, sorghum, rice and maize by measuring 100 grams of each starch material sourced from the different agricultural products which were hydrolyzed using 6 M hydrochloric acid respectively. The resultant reducing sugar (glucose) solution were fermented using brewer's yeast and then distilled to obtain alcohol (ethanol). The yield of alcohol was determined, which ranged from 19.40 – 7.00 %. Sorghum gave the highest yield of 19.40 % which rice gave least yield of alcohol of 7.00 %. The daily protein analysis of the fermenting liquor was irregular, however the daily glucose analysis showed a gradual decrease in the concentration of glucose as fermentation progresses.

Key words: Cassava, Sorghum, Rice, Maize, Alcohol, Fermentation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The history of alcohol is perhaps longer and more involved than that of any natural product. Though they do not occur in nature, they are however synthesized from naturally occurring substances and other already synthesized substances in the laboratory.

Alcohol are produced either from natural products such as fermentation of carbohydrates and reductive cleavage of fat and oil, or by chemical synthesis from petroleum or synthesis of gas from coal (Mark, *et al.*, 2012).

The fermentation of sugars and starch (carbohydrates) to produce alcoholic beverages has been employed since recorded history. The industrial fermentation process is the biological transformation of carbohydrates by yeast to produce the desired product such as ethanol or 1-butanol and acetone (Mark, *et al.*, 2012).

Ethyl alcohol or ethanol ranks second only to water as the most widely used solvent in

chemical industry and as these industries expand, so the demand for industrial alcohol. Alcohol acts as a solvent for an immense range of industrial products, including paints, lacquers, dyes and oils. In addition, some are used as a raw material in chemical synthesis and a little in the form of fuel (Rose, 1961).

In 1935, a Brazilian scientist, Lauro de Baros Siciliano, made a proposal for the use of alcohol as fuel for the internal combustion engines as a way of conserving the mineral fuel.

The rising cost of oil in the last few years and the concerns of climate change have led to an increasing interest in renewable sources of energy like biofuel which can substitute fossil fuel to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on oil producing countries.

The biofuel that are currently in use, known as first generation biofuel, are mainly produced from sugarcane, maize or soy. The main

producers are Brazil and USA. Bioethanol, produced from sugarcane, maize, pineapple, banana and biodiesel, produced from soybeans, sunflower, corn oil are presently produced on an industrial scale (Hossain, *et al.*, 2008, Hossain and Fazliny, 2010, Hossain and Boyce, 2009).

Alcohol (Ethanol) is widely used as a solvent in stains and polishes. Ethanol when “denatured” by naphtha and wood spirit (methanol) and coloured purple is used as methylated spirit (Morrison, *et al.*, 1974).

The huge fluctuations in the price of petroleum within the past twenty years have made commercial production of fermentation ethanol more attractive. Due to the current interest in the economic conversion of renewable resources into alcohol, residues of a number of crops were evaluated as substrates for alcohol production (Han & Cho 1983, Jones, *et al.*, 1981).

Any agricultural product that contains sugar in any form can be fermented to give ethanol (alcohol) hence, cassava, sorghum, rice and maize as the raw materials.

Since alcohol (ethanol) is a potential source for the future in the face of diminishing conventional energy sources, this project is aimed at the possibility of sourcing alcohol from some locally selected agricultural products containing sugar; and analyzing the various percentages of alcohol obtained from the selected agricultural products.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The raw material used for the research were powdered starch gotten from cassava, maize, rice and sorghum, the cassava was collected from a farm in Abraka town while the rice, maize and sorghum were obtained from Efurun market. The cassava tuber was peeled, washed

and then milled into a pulp by means of a commercial grinding machine. The pulp was suspended in water for 20 mins., after which the fibrous materials were removed; more water was added to the milk and passed through a wire sieve to remove the smaller fibrous materials while the starch was left to settle in a container overnight and later allowed to dry under the sun for some days (Ray, *et al.*, 2009, Ocloo and Ayernor, 2008). Similarly, the rice, maize and sorghum were dried under the sun and then taken to the commercial grinding machine and ground to powered form.

100 grams of the starch material was dissolved in 200 ml of distill water in a 1000 ml beaker. 40 ml of 6 M HCL was added and the mixture heated with a flame; while heating, a total of 400 ml of distilled water was added with continuous stirring to prevent the starch solution from forming a paste. At interval of 5 mins. part of the boiling solution was collected and tested with the iodine solution. The change in colour from the blue-black starch colour to iodine’s original colour indicates the absence of starch and confirms the presence of glucose, thus confirming complete hydrolysis of the starch solution; However, when compared with others, the hydrolysis of cassava took a longer period (Aloys, *et al.*, 2006, Victor, 2010).

The resultant solution was then filtered and kept overnight in an airtight container to prevent contamination by atmospheric microorganisms. A few minutes before the commencement of the fermentation process, freshly, prepared 2 M solution of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was added to neutralize (remove) any excess acid used during hydrolysis and a universal indicator paper for approximate pH determination was used to

confirm the neutralization. The solution was again filtered; the resultant solution (glucose solution) was then used for the fermentation process. This was done for all the samples (Aloys, *et al.*, 2006, Maiorella, *ete al.*, 1981).

2.1.Fermentation Process

The glucose solution obtained from the hydrolytic process was placed in a desiccator in order to keep oxygen out of the fermenting liquors (Robert, *et al.*,1981).Then 90 ml of freshly prepared Pasteur's salt and 20 g of the brewer's yeast was added to the solution and kept in a cupboard for eight (8) days. The cupboard supplies the warmth needed for the fermentation process. Samples of the fermenting liquor (otherwise known as "must") were collected on a daily basis throughout the fermentation process for the protein and glucose concentration analysis. At completion of the fermentation, the liquor was filtered in such a way that none of the sediment appears in the liquor. The filtrate was then taken to a simple distillation process.

2.2. Biuret Quantitative Test for Total Protein:

0.1 ml of the test solution was diluted to 0.2 ml of distilled water and was added to 5 ml of the biuret reagent in a test tube, the content was mixed thoroughly and incubated for 15minutes at 37 °C. It was then cooled to room temperature. The absorbance at 550 nm against a reagent blank was recorded. The concentration of the total protein was extrapolated from the protein standard curve (Plummer *et al.*, 1988).

2.3. Determination of Carbohydrate (Glucose) by Anthrone Method

0.2 ml of the protein free carbohydrate extracted solution was diluted to 0.1 ml with distilled water in a test tube and was mixed thoroughly, the 4.0 ml Anthrone reagent was added to it, and the test-tube was placed in boiling water for 10 minutes with a cork to prevent loss of water via evaporation. The test tube was later cooled and absorbance at 620 nm against a reagent blank was recorded (David, 1990). A glucose standard curve was prepared and a graph of absorbance against concentration of the standard glucose was plotted. The glucose concentration was then extrapolated from the glucose standard curve. The distillation was carried out and the distillate was collected off at 100 °C. This distillate contains all the alcohol and the residue was discarded. The distillate was then transferred to a conical flask containing a few lumps for fresh calcium oxide and calcium, the flask was corked and left to stand for twelve hours, after which it was redistilled and collected between 78-79 °C and the fraction was reasonably pure alcohol (ethanol).

2.4. Distinguishing Test for Ethanol

Five (5) drops of the ethanol were added to 5 ml of iodine solution in a test tube, this was followed by the addition of sodium hydroxide solution carefully until the colour faded away. The test tube was placed in a water bath of 70 °C for 2 to 3 minutes and allowed to cool. The yellow crystals were the iodoform and the smell was reminiscent of antiseptic. This reaction does not occur with methanol (Fuson, *et al.*, 1934).

Tri-iodomethane

(Iodofom)

2.5. Percentage yield of Alcohol (Ethanol) from each Product.

The volume of alcohol gotten from each product were recorded and their yield calculated based on the weight of the material used(vol./weight).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Alcohol content

Table 1: Percentage yield of alcohol

S/N	ALCOHOL CONTENT (ml)	ALCOHOL CONTENT (ml)	PERCENTAGE YIELD (vol./wt.)%
1	Cassava	16.16	16.60
2	Maize	11.10	11.10
3	Rice	7.00	7.00
4	Sorghum	19.40	19.40

Table 2: Standard curve for protein determination.

S/N	TUBE NUMBER	STANDARD PROTEIN SOLUTION (ml)	DISTILLED WATER(ml)	ABSORBANCE	PROTEIN CONCENTRATION (mg/ml)
1	0	0.00	2.00	0.00	0.00
2	1	0.20	1.80	0.017	0.06
3	2	0.40	1.60	0.034	0.12
4	3	0.60	1.40	0.056	0.18
5	4	0.80	1.20	0.072	0.24
6	5	1.00	1.00	0.088	0.30
7	6	1.20	0.80	0.109	0.36
8	7	1.40	0.60	0.122	0.42
9	8	1.60	0.40	0.140	0.48
10	9	1.80	0.20	0.158	0.54
11	10	2.00	0.00	0.175	0.60

The protein analysis of the fermenting liquor; The concentration of the protein for the standard curve was calculated as follows: Standard stock protein was 0.3 mg/ml i.e. 1ml of the standard protein solution gives 0.3 mg protein.

Therefore, 0.2 ml of the standard protein gives

$$0.3 \times 0.2/1 = 0.6 \text{ mg/ml protein} \quad (1)$$

A plot of absorbance against the concentration of protein curve is where the various concentration was determined as presented below:

Table 3: Protein Analysis of Sorghum and Cassava

S/N	NUMBER OF DAYS	ABSORBANCE OF SORGHUM	PROTEIN CONCENTRATION (mg/ml) OF SORGHUM	ABSORBANCE OF CASSAVA	PROTEIN CONCENTRATION (mg/ml) OF CASSAVA
1	1	0.136	0.480	0.020	0.060
2	2	0.044	0.132	0.011	0.030
3	3	0.043	0.132	0.000	0.000
4	4	0.045	0.168	0.005	0.030
5	5	0.114	0.372	0.000	0.000
6	6	0.056	0.201	0.00	0.000
7	7	0.068	0.240	0.010	0.030
8	8	0.075	0.270	0.008	0.030
9	9	0.090	0.300	0.050	0.158

Day 1: Before the commencement of the fermentation process.

Day 9: Before the commencement of the distillation process.

Table 4: Protein analysis of Maize and Rice

S/N	NUMBER OF DAYS	ABSORBANCE OF MAIZE	PROTEIN CONCENTRATION (mg/ml) OF MAIZE	ABSORBANCE OF RICE	PROTEIN CONCENTRATION (mg/ml) OF RICE
1	1	0.140	0.480	0.022	0.060
2	2	0.012	0.030	0.011	0.030
3	3	0.013	0.030	0.006	0.030
4	4	0.015	0.060	0.014	0.030
5	5	0.012	0.030	0.008	0.030
6	6	0.014	0.030	0.009	0.030
7	7	0.019	0.060	0.004	0.000
8	8	0.043	0.132	0.016	0.060
9	9	0.032	0.096	0.084	0.210

GLUCOSE ANALYSIS OF THE FERMENTING LIQUOR

The glucose concentration for the standard curve was calculated as follows:

Standard stock glucose solution contains 0.1 mg glucose.

Therefore, 0.2 ml of the standard glucose solution contains:

$$0.1 \times 0.2/1 = 0.02 \text{ mg/ml} \quad (2)$$

Table 5: Standard curve for glucose determination

S/N	TUBE NUMBER	STANDARD GLUCOSE SOLUTION (ml)	DISTILLED WATER (ml)	ABSORBNCE	GLUCOSE CONCENTRATION (mg/ml)
1	0	0.00	1.00	0.000	0.000
2	1	0.20	0.80	0.040	0.020
3	2	0.40	0.60	0.069	0.040
4	3	0.60	0.40	0.120	0.060
5	4	0.80	0.20	0.154	0.080
6	5	1.00	0.00	0.214	0.100

A plot of absorbance against the concentration of glucose curve is where the various concentration was determine as presented in the following tables

Table 6: Glucose analysis of Sorghum and Cassava

S/N	NUMBER OF DAYS	ABSORBANCE OF SORGHUM	GLUCOSE CONCENTRATION (mg/ml) OF SORGHUM	ABSORBANCE OF RICE	GLUCOSE CONCENTRATION (mg/ml) OF CASSAVA
1	1	0.384	0.192	0.398	0.196
2	2	0.241	0.122	0.252	0.127
3	3	0.162	0.080	0.173	0.086
4	4	0.106	0.057	0.110	0.055
5	5	0.087	0.046	0.089	0.045
6	6	0.058	0.030	0.066	0.035
7	7	0.042	0.020	0.054	0.025
8	8	0.041	0.020	0.051	0.025
9	9	0.040	0.020	0.051	0.025

Table 7: Glucose analysis of Maize and Rice

S/N	NUMBER OF DAYS	ABSORBANCE OF MAIZE	GLUCOSE CONCENTRATION (mg/ml) OF MAIZE	ABSORBANCE OF RICE	GLUCOSE CONCENTRATION (mg/ml) OF RICE
1	1	0.209	0.106	0.354	0.176
2	2	0.116	0.060	0.243	0.122
3	3	0.090	0.045	0.175	0.092
4	4	0.081	0.040	0.115	0.060
5	5	0.076	0.040	0.100	0.050
6	6	0.061	0.030	0.087	0.045
7	7	0.051	0.025	0.062	0.030
8	8	0.050	0.025	0.014	0.005
9	9	0.049	0.025	0.013	0.005

Table 1 shows that 100 g of different starch materials yielded different alcohol (ethanol), however, sorghum grain gave the highest percentage yield of 19.40 % while rice gave the least percentage yield of 7.00 %. Though, cassava have been found to be one of the richest fermentable raw materials for the production of alcohol, this should be as a result of the delay in the conversion of starch of cassava into glucose within the same duration during hydrolysis when compared with sorghum as shown in Table 1. The colour change of starch into iodine's colour indicates the complete absence of starch and complete conversion to glucose during hydrolysis which was faster in the case of sorghum; thus, sorghum when hydrolyzed within the same duration as the others, starch samples, contained more glucose molecules in solution, and since the volume of alcohol obtain from fermentation is a function of the quantity of glucose, sorghum gave the highest yield of alcohol. The daily protein analysis of the fermenting liquor shows an irregular pattern as shown in Tables 3 and 4 but the result revealed that sorghum has the highest concentration of protein among the raw materials used. Table 3 and 4 revealed that sorghum has the highest protein concentration value of 0.300mg/ml before the commencement of distillation process while maize has the least protein concentration value. Sorghum has the highest protein concentration before the commencement of fermentation and distillation processes with values of 0.480 mg/ml and 0.300 mg/ml respectively.

Table 3 and 4 revealed that sorghum and maize were having the same protein concentration value of 0.480 mg/ml while cassava and rice the same protein concentration value of 0.060

mg/ml but as the days of fermentation progresses the protein concentration changes. The biuret determination was employed in the protein analysis, though not very effective compared to the Lowry's and Kjeldahl's method, but was chosen because of its relative cheapness and availability of the needed materials. The daily glucose analysis carried out to monitor the progress of fermentation as observed in Tables 6 and 7 showed a gradual decrease in the concentration of the glucose indicating the progress of fermentation. Table 6 and 7 revealed that cassava and maize has the same glucose concentration of 0.025 mg/ml while rice has the least value of concentration of 0.005 mg/ml. The decrease observed in the glucose concentration was as a result of the effective activities of the yeast used during fermentation. The yeast cells feeds on the glucose content converting glucose into alcohol. Thus, decreasing the glucose concentration of the fermenting liquor as the day increases. Sorghum with the highest alcohol percentage yield of 19.40 % has the highest protein concentration value of 0.300 mg/ml but with glucose concentration of 0.020 mg/ml before commencement of distillation process.

4. CONCLUSION

The study was designed to compare the yield and analysis of alcohol from the various agricultural products with respect to the quantity of the sample of starch used. The results in Table 1 revealed that sorghum, cassava, maize and rice are substrates for the production of alcohol. However, this research work has provided additional information and experience to the body of knowledge available on the process of hydrolysis and fermentation. The efficiency of fermentation or the yield of

ethanol production is a function of the time, concentration of yeast and optimum conditions as described in the result and discussion section.

Sorghum and cassava could therefore serve as some additional raw materials for alcohol production, although presently, enough is not being produced for both consumption and as raw material. This work also encourages research into less expensive carbohydrates for the production of alcohol, which is valuable as fuel, industrial reagent, beverages and also consider the use of sorghum because of its high protein content.

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